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RESULTS OF TRAINING IN THE TRIAGE SYSTEM OF MEDICAL WORKERS OF KAZAKHSTAN ON THE BASIS OF THE TRAINING AND CLINICAL CENTER OF THE SEMEY MEDICAL UNIVERSITY, NCJSC FOR 2018-2025

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Relevance: A large number of people die due to the lack of qualified medical care at the pre-hospital stage, which determines the increasing role of emergency medical care for the population in the healthcare system. Given the fact that pre-hospital mortality remains high, in Kazakhstan, since July 2017, the modernization of the ambulance service has begun. In order to improve the quality of emergency medical care in Kazakhstan, a new format of hospital admission departments has been introduced, based on strengthening the triage sorting of patients and the readiness to accept patients with any form of pathology. According to the order of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 450 "On approval of the Rules for the provision of emergency medical care in the Republic of Kazakhstan" dated July 3, 2017, a triage system model of a new type of admission department was created on the basis of the State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Semey State Medical University" (currently - SMU, NCJSC) to form a theoretical basis for training emergency specialists of a new format, which is the first Triage Training Zone in Kazakhstan.

The aim of the work: to study the prevalence of training of medical workers in the triage system of patients in Kazakhstan.

Materials and methods of the study: Design - retrospective study. Continuous sample (n=878 people who completed the training). A retrospective analysis of statistical data of people who completed the training for 2018-2025 was conducted according to the data of the Department of Simulation Technologies of SMU, NCJSC.

Research results: A total of 878 students from the Mangystau, Karaganda, Kyzylorda, Kostanay, Akmola, Aktobe, Pavlodar regions, the cities of Aktau, Pavlodar, Karaganda, Kyzylorda and Semey, Petropavlovsk, Astana, Kostanay, Aksu, and the Urzhar district were trained in the "Triage of patients by the severity of an emergency condition" cycle. Of these, 512 were trained in 2018, 326 in 2019, 11 in 2020, 33 in 2022, and 4 medical workers in 2023-2025. The redesign of the emergency medicine department in the following medical institutions has also been agreed upon: City Hospital No. 1 in Pavlodar, State Enterprise Aktobe Medical Center in Aktobe, Republican State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "City Hospital No. 1" in Astana, East Kazakhstan Regional Hospital in Ust-Kamenogorsk, State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Mangystau Regional Hospital" in Aktau, "Regional Clinical Hospital" in Karaganda, State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Regional Hospital in Taldykorgan", State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Regional Medical Center" in Kyzylorda, Republican State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management City Hospital of Emergency Care in Almaty. The following facilities are in progress: State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Regional Hospital of the City of Taldykorgan" in Taldykorgan, State Enterprise on the Right of Economic Management "Regional Clinical Hospital" of Uralsk, Central Hospital of Temirtau, State Enterprise on Right of

Economic Management Atyrau Regional Hospital of Atyrau, State Enterprise Kostanay Regional Hospital of Kostanay Region.

Conclusions: The functional design of the emergency medical care department and triage of patients by the severity of the emergency condition is an innovation in education and healthcare, modernization of the educational process in accordance with modern requirements. The functional design of the emergency medicine department at the Department of Simulation Technologies of the SMU, NCJSC is designed for the full training of students, interns, residents, teachers and medical workers throughout Kazakhstan.